

ANTICIPATED WILDFIRE: POLITICAL DEFECTION AND ONE PARTY SYSTEM IN NIGERIA; FROM DE FACTO “AUTHORITARIAN DEMOCRACY” TO OLIGARCHY

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Abstract: Political defection in Nigeria with its attendant one party system has become more frequent and prevalent especially within the last two years. The effects of political defection on the country’s fledgling democracy is enormous and likely to usher in dictatorial and authoritarian regime. Therefore, this study critically examined political defection and one party system in Nigeria from de facto authoritarian democracy to oligarchy. The study adopted mixed method which involved eliciting data from primary and secondary sources. Z-test statistical tool was used to test the formulated hypotheses. The dangers of political defections were properly interrogated by the researchers. Major findings revealed that political defection is likely to lead to misrule and governance deficit, also, the study revealed that political defection will further expose Nigeria’s weak democratic structure. Based on the foregoing, the researchers suggested the following among others; that the electorates should ensure that they get their voters card and come out to vote. The Civil Society Organisations (CSOs) should speak out on this evil political development in Nigeria which if not arrested would result to dictatorship, anarchy and chaos. It is also the position of the researchers that the ethnic groups in Nigeria should eschew ethnic jingoism, and close ranks with the masses to fight this hydra headed monster and nip it in the bud.

1, Introduction

Nigeria, former giant of Africa and former largest economy in Africa, once again is at a cross-roads.

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The ruling party, All Progressive Congress (APC) which is currently suffocating the masses of Nigeria with misrule, governance deficit, anti-people policies and programs has ridiculously boxed other political parties in Nigeria to a corner with ignominy. The party is operating freely without organised opposition as obtains in other nascent democracies across the globe (Chukwuemeka, Dike and Edokobi, 2021).

The recent mass exodus of top Nigerian politicians from opposition parties to the ruling All Progressives Congress (APC) has had an unsettling effect in the Nigerian polity. As at the last count, the People's Democratic Party (PDP) was almost depleted, with most of its Governors and legislators moving to APC one after the other (Adamu, 2023). Party officials from other parties, have since joined the bandwagon. What could be the reasons behind this unprecedented movements? Is Nigeria headed towards a sycophantic one-party system? What does it portend for Nigeria's fledgling democracy?

During the first republic, the major political parties involved in the general election were United Peoples Grand Alliance (UPGA), the United Progressive Front (NPC), and the Nigerian National Alliance (NNA) made up of NPC, NNDP, a split from Action Group, Mid-Western People's Congress and Dynamic party (Chukwuemeka, 2008). During the second republic, politicians were more as serious as they were in the first republic, and determined to serve their people. They also towered strong in

their political parties without wavering contends, Chukwuemeka, (2022), whether they win in the federal election or not, they do not defect to another party. For instance during the second republic, there were five major political parties in Nigeria: National Party of Nigeria (ruling party), the party flag bearer was Alhaji Shehu Shagari, Nigerian Peoples Party, the party flag bearer was Dr/ Benjamin Nnamdi Azikiwe, Peoples Redemption Party, flag bearer was Malam Aminu Kano, Unity Party of Nigeria with Chief Obafemi Awolowo as flag bearer and Great Nigerian Peoples Party, flag bearer was Ibrahim Waziri. Members of the aforementioned parties were committed and steadfast with their parties while working to win the presidential seat. Members did not defect to the ruling party NPN in spite the fact that they lost in the two federal elections held in 1979 and 1983 respectively (Chukwuemeka, Oji and Chukwurah 2014). But today we have noticed a flagrant defection to any party controlling the presidency. Many political parties in Nigeria today have collapsed their structures with the ruling party- APC. Some members of other parties have shamefully defected to APC. We are not talking of anti-party activities, like the case of former Governor of Rivers State who is literarily in PDP but have loyalty for APC

1.2 Statement of the Problem

The rate of defection of politicians to the ruling All Progressive Congress (APC) is worrisome and have left nothing to be desired. Anti-party

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activities have been witnessed in most of the political parties in Nigeria. A cursory look at the political landscape of Nigeria today is more like the maxim 'if you cannot beat them, you join them'. This ugly political development is highly pronounced among the disgruntled and corrupt politicians in Nigeria. Some few years back, the People Democratic Party had the highest membership, but as soon as PDP lost the presidential election in 2019, there has been a noticeable defection of members to the ruling party APC. As of 15th October, 2025, political party score board across Nigerian geo-political zones stands as follows:

APC – 24 states

PDP – 8 states

Others- 4 states

Some of the thought provoking questions are: to what extent mass political defection has affected Nigeria's 'authoritarian democracy? Is mass political defection not turning Nigeria into oligarchic and dictatorial regime? The tendency in this ill political development is that misrule is likely to be heightened, corruption is likely to be heightened and also suppression of the masses may be the end result of the impending one party system in Nigeria. The issue of bad governance and suppression of the voices of the civil society organizations, the media and the Nigerian aggrieved non governing elites may not be overruled. It is a dangerous politics to suppress all forms of opposition and also the use of the armed forces against the masses when they

attempt to embark on peaceful protest to vent their anger on flagrant misrule in Nigeria.

1.3 Objectives of the Study

(1) To examine the extent mass political defection and its attendant one party system in Nigeria could lead to misrule and governance deficit

(2) To determine the extent mass defection to the ruling APC and its attendant one party system could lead to authoritarianism and dictatorship

1.4 Hypotheses

(1) Mass defection and its attendant one party system in Nigeria will lead to misrule and governance deficit

(2) Mass defection to the ruling party and its attendant one party system in Nigeria is a prelude to authoritarianism and dictatorship.

2. Review of Related Literature

2.1 Interrogating the concept, political defection

According to Black's Law Dictionary cited in Otoyebi, (2024), defection has been defined as abandonment of allegiance or duty, the forsaking of a person or cause, desertion. In other words, defection is the act of abandoning one's allegiance for another. In political terms, it can mean the forsaking of one's political party for the opposition.

Political defection seems to have become a recurring feature in Nigerian politics. It is a custom that predates Nigeria independence as a Country. As far back as 1951, few members of the

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pre-independence political parties defected to rival political parties in a bid to secure their interests. While it is true that politicians have the fundamental right to freedom of association, it is still pertinent to note that certain rights come with limitations. Scholars have continuously agitated for the enactment of proper laws that will curtail the rate of political defections, but this has not been addressed as defections are still on the rise (Atoyebi, 2024).

Some causes of political defection in Nigeria

Political defection in Nigeria has become a decimal phenomenon in Nigeria political landscape and it is at verge of turning Nigeria into one party system. According Chukwuemeka, Oji and Chukwurah (2013), political defection in Nigeria can be associated with the following:

(a) Greed among contemporary politicians: The new brand of politicians in Nigeria are avaricious and full of inordinate ambition to amass wealth through stealing of public fund. Therefore, when their political party fails to capture political power, they easily defect to the ruling party.

(b) Lack of integrity and pedigree: Most contemporary politicians in Nigeria do not have integrity and pedigree, and therefore they believe that the only way to become politically relevant is by defecting to the government in power (JGP)

(c) Political ideology: Some contemporary politicians wallow in confusion of ideology. Most

political parties in Nigeria do not have properly articulated manifesto let alone having any political ideology (Chukwuemeka, 2017)..

(d) Unemployment: most of the politicians do not have job, or even if they have, some have jobs that are not stable. Conversely, some who are professionals abandon their cherished and lucrative profession to politics because they believe that it is the easiest way to get rich by stealing public fund. Therefore, politics for them is the only way out for massive economic sustainability.

(e) Changing morals of politicians – the cherished tradition of elected representative dying for the people is no longer tenable. The people are dying for their ‘honorable’. Our politicians prefer setting the whole house on fire provided the rat is caught. The reminiscences of Zik, Awolowo, Okpara, Balewa are now fairy tales. Today’s politicians in Nigeria will prefer to kill all the citizens provided they have their way (Chukwuemeka, 2017).

(f) Weak electoral institutions and lack of accountability: The electoral umpire in Nigeria - Independent National Electoral Commission and other electoral agencies in Nigeria find it difficult to implement electoral laws and reforms, to ensure that the interest of the ruling party that appointed them is protected. Some of the people appointed into the electoral institutions are members of the ruling party.

(g) Political survival and career advancement: Most of the Nigerian politicians strive to survive

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at all cost. The shameless, disgruntled and gullible politicians easily shift to the ruling party to protect their selfish interest.

(h) Inability to pursue political ideology: Most political parties in Nigeria do not have ideology, manifesto compared to those in organized democracies. Because they have no ideology to protect, they easily shift to the ruling party when the storm is high.

Political defection: Impediments and imbroglio

Political defection has numerous effects on the Nigerian fledgling democratic system. Political defection creates a tendency towards a one-party state where the ruling party dominates the democratic system almost completely (Ibrahim 2023), Political defection contends (Diepreye and Oputa 2025) impair the election process by creating an unequal playing field. Thus, the dominant party gets an unfair advantage via greater access to state resources, media dominance, and political patronage. The opposition parties are deprived of their best members. What happened in 2023 election is a case in point, where APC the ruling party hijacked the electoral umpire INEC, the media, the judiciary and other institutions, used the state resources to impose itself on the people.

Accountability and Stewardship: Also, the issue of accountability is another serious issue. One party dominance diminishes the efficacy of checks and balances resulting to a lack of accountability.

Voters Apathy: Voters apathy and disillusionment is yet another impediment. When electorates spent their good time to stand in queue to vote, at the end of the day their votes did not count like what happened in 2023 election. Next time you call the electorates out to vote, they will not turn up.

There is no gainsaying it that political defection makes Nigeria to stand in the risk of authoritarianism and dictatorship.

Political defection, one party system and good governance: The Nexus

Good governance refers to “a set of qualitative characteristics relating to processes of rulemaking and their institutional foundations. It encapsulates values such as enhanced participation, transparency, accountability, and public access to information. It also helps to combat corruption and secure both basic human rights and the rule of law” (UNU-IAS in Dhaoui, 2019).

|||imbroglio, high profile kidnapping, dastardly activities of unknown gunmen, boko haram, cultism, armed robbery high suicide rate, banditry, ritual killing, ethnic militarism, ethnic jingoism etc.

Nowadays, it is widely recognized that a single model of governance cannot and should not be imposed. The main reason is that governance varies across contexts and cultures, and has evolved in response to a number of socio-cultural and economic factors.

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Good public governance and a more efficient and effective public administration are key drivers for smart, inclusive and sustainable growth, which are the aims of the 2030 strategy.

The Nigeria economic crisis has negatively affected already strained government resources and posed challenges in the area of democratic governance. According to the Organisation for Economic Cooperation and Development (OECD) Nigeria has experienced increased income inequality since the onset of the crisis. Unemployment is high, especially among young people. Vulnerable groups of all ages and both sexes are being hit by the crisis. Inter-regional differences in public services and regional disparities combined with significant differences in fiscal capacities have deepened.

Within the framework of the 2030 strategy, national public administration reform programmes are seen as instruments to improve democratic and economic governance and foster fiscal consolidation. They are essential for structural reforms required, for investment in growth and employment and for improved service delivery. They also help to achieve a better balance between economic interests, environmental concerns and social inclusion.

Governments in Nigeria are faced with a loss of trust in their ability to deal with the crisis and met citizens' needs and expectations. This loss of trust can reduce the effectiveness of policies and ultimately undermine the capacity of government to uphold fundamental rights. Good

public governance, including the rule of law, contributes to building trust and confidence in national institutions as stewards of national well-being, quality of life and economic prosperity for citizens.

13.1 Stress areas in good governance include:

- (a) Institutional capacity- building
- (b) Public administration reform
- (c) Delivery, accessibility and quality of public services
- (d) Accountable, inclusive and transparent government
- (e) Economic and financial governance
- (f) Cooperation between government and civil society

13.2 The Effect of Good Governance on Development

Regarding the effect of good governance on economic growth and development, there have been many studies that talked about this nexus. Results differ according to the regions and according to the used econometric tools. Some studies found a non-conclusive link. Others found a negative relationship. However, the majority of studies have shown a positive and a direct effect to achieve development targets such as reducing poverty, increasing employment, more equitable redistribution of income, etc (Chukwuemeka, 2021).

Actually, there are widely accepted arguments that governance should play a stronger role in the post-2015 development agenda starting from

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the premises that good governance enables the achievement of a range of important development objectives.

Nowadays, the ongoing discussion recognizes that current development challenges are more complex. Indeed, and according to the SDGs agenda, sustainable development should concern economic, social and environmental dimensions. Also, this development should be equitable.

Fig. 1: Underpinning of Good Governance

> Mechanism of good governance include: transparent and democratic institutions, efficient and effective public services.

> Governance processes refer to: the quality of participation necessary to ensure that political, social and economic priorities are based on a broad consensus in society and that the voices of the excluded, poorest, and most vulnerable are heard in decision-making.

> Outcomes of good governance could be peaceful, stable and resilient societies, where services are delivered and reflect the needs of communities, including the voices of the most vulnerable and marginalized.

Integrating e-governance with sustainable development could include:

Good governance is widely acknowledged as a foundation for sustainable development, including sustained and inclusive economic growth, social development, environmental protection and the eradication of poverty and hunger.

To ascertain whether governance is good, their dimensions have to be assessed: Mechanisms that promote it, the process used, and the outcomes achieved.

- (a) Protecting basic rights of citizens and creation of valued services for higher living standards of people.
- (b) For genuine development in society, sustainability is crucial
- (c) Pursuit of sustainability depends on the government integrating many services and providing one-step, critical service to citizens.
- (d) Efficiency is necessary to make things as simple as possible yet beneficial as possible as well.
- (e) Transparency and accountability are important characteristics of decision making for sustainability.

Indicators and Requirements for Good Governance

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Enhancing governance requires some actions in different areas, not all of which can address at once, and all can be the subject of a global consensus:

- (a) Effective, responsive and accountable state institutions
- (b) Openness and transparency – public access to information
- (c) Addressing corruption and curbing illicit financial flows
- (d) Participation in decision making
- (e) Curbing violence and combating transnational and national organized crime
- (f) Presence of opposition to bring good governance
- (g) Multi -party system
- (h) Allowing citizens peaceful protest and carrying of placards
- (i) Sensitive to public opinion
- (i) Free press
- (j) Regular and free and fair election
- (k) Making electoral umpire independent

(l) Independent of the judiciary and Legislative arms of government (principles of checks and balances)

For the implementation of good governance principles, a special attention is towards institutions. In this regard, institutions must help citizens achieve sustainability by, especially, providing equal opportunities and ensuring social, economic and political access to resources. Institutions, especially public ones, could contribute heavily to the maintenance of human rights, environmental protection, stable macroeconomic conditions, enhance health conditions, manage and mobilise resource for essential public services, etc (Juknevcienė and Kratėvaite, 2012). Further, it is crucial to identify problems, develop frameworks and create opportunities, and create the open-government ideas and formatting an appropriate public policy (Chukwuemeka, 2022, 2019). Therefore, formal institutions are emphasized in the implementation process of sustainable development concept.

Fig. 3: Classification of Institutional Indicators (quantitative and qualitative)

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- Corruption
- Civil and political Freedom
- Rule of law

The term governance is often characterized by seven major characteristics which assure that corruption is minimized, the view of communities is taken into account, and the

voices of the most vulnerable in society are heard. As for the indicators of good governance, graph below stated clearly the most important indicators:

Fig.4 Good Governance Indicators

One party system and Nigerian “Authoritarian democracy”

To sum the discourse, it is evident that there is a disconnect between political defection and good

governance in Nigeria. Without any equivocation, it is right to say that Nigeria has degenerated to authoritarian democracy and oligarchy (Anikwe, Ogbuke and Udentia, 2025).

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It is therefore evident that the three arms of government have been collapsed into the executive arm of government. Judiciary is not independent, the legislative arm is an extended arm of the executive, the Nigerian Senate and House of Representatives today are mere 'rubber stamp' or well, could be described as pseudo law marking arm of government.

What Nigeria experienced during the military dictatorship and oligarchic regime of General Sani Abacha is trying to rear its ugly head again. Between 1993 and 1998 Nigeria had a military head of state, Sani Abacha, who ruled as a maximum dictator. He would eventually yield to pressure to transition the country to a democracy, but he also plotted to succeed himself as the president. Keenly aware that he was unpopular and had no chance of winning the presidency in any free and fair election under a multiparty democracy, Abacha turned to unholy schemes. His regime staged an aggressive montage of propaganda to lauder his image behind a façade of positive narratives- all suggesting a show of overwhelming public support for the military head of state to succeed himself. They portrayed him as the best leader ever and his candidacy as the second coming of the Messiah. But that was not all.

Buoyed by the false public support, General Abacha used the instrument of power to coerce opposing political parties to endorse him as a sole candidate. All coasts were clear for him to enthrone a sham democracy featuring only one

party and, of course, without internal or external opposition. But providence has a way with destiny, as well as with ambitions. Sani Abacha died unexpectedly in 1998. And his brand of democracy also died suddenly, or so we thought. It is evident that this mass defection to the ruling party is a ploy to replicate the Abacha saga 1998. The objective fact is that the Abacha model of democracy is back. The political calculation of the ruling party –APC is to make Nigeria one party system by trick.

Calamity of Single party dominance

This system is usually established through a constitutional provision making one party the only recognized party in the country. What happened in Nigeria in April 2023 general election, where All Progressive Congress (APC) had a false land slide victory in all the positions looked like a 'forced' one party system (Chukwuemeka, Ewuim, Ukeje 2020). However what happened could be described as 'election maneuver'. One party system in essence, is evil, especially in a fledgling democracy like Nigeria. Some of the pitfalls are:

- (i) It creates room for bad governance
- (ii) It is devoid of opposition, which increase room for sycophancy.
- (iii) It heightens ethnic conflict, since the disadvantaged and marginalized ethnic groups would always agitate either for self-determination or outright separation from the federal system

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(iv) Peace is not guaranteed, mass protest is heightened

(v) It leaves the government in the hands of an oligarchy thus marginalizing the masses.

(vi) Dictatorship is a dangerous and well documented outcome of one party system

(vii) One common danger of long term one party dominance is the tendency to move into group-think. The lack of exploration, yet alone the adoption of viable advantageous alternative is a common negative by-product of such a closed system/

(viii) The creativity of thesis-antithesis=synthesis is often absent in such systems. Given the trickledown effect of elected officials on bureaucracy it can take generations

for any needed change in the status quo to be implemented.

(ix) Such systems are more easily corrupted by backroom dealing. Out right favoritism for political bakers is more prevalent in such systems. Lack of responsiveness to citizens, groups or geographic areas who are not part of “The club” is often a result. Muhammadu Buhari marginalized the Igbo ethnic group because he claimed that they did not vote for him.

These and many more calamities are common feature of one party system. Today, the ruling party (APC) has hijacked other parties in Nigeria. This is a dangerous political development.

Table 2.1: Data on political defection in Nigeria as at 15th October 2025

SN	State	Party Defected to	Geo-Political Zone
1	Delta State	APC	South-South
2	Akwa Ibom	APC	
3	Edo	APC	
4	Cross River	APC	
5	Rivers	PDD (Pseudo)	
6	Balyelsa	APC	
7	Enugu	APC	South-East
8	Ebonyi	APC	
9	Imo	APC	
10	Abia	Labour Party	
11	Anambra	APGA	
12	Lagos	APC	South-West
13	Ekiti	APC	
14	Ogun	APC	
15	Oyo	PDP	

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16	Ondo	APC	
17	Osun	PDP	
18	Benue	APC	North-Central
19	Niger	APC	
20	Nasarawa	APC	
21	Kwara	APC	
22	Kogi	APC	
23	Plateau	PDP	
24	Borno	APC	North=East
25	Yobe	APC	
26	Taraba	PDP	
27	Gombe	APC	
28	Adamawa	PDP	
29	Bauchi	PDP	
30	Katsina	APC	North=West
31	Jigawa	APC	
32	Kebbi	APC	
33	Kaduna	APC	
34	Zamfara	PDP	
35	Kano	NNPP	
36	Sokoto	APC	

Source: Researchers field survey (2025)

From the table above, we can deduce that APC has 28 states out of 36 states in Nigeria, APGA has 1 state, NNPP has 1 state, Labour Party has 1 state, and PDP has 5 states. It is being envisaged that before the 2027 general election, all the political party members in Nigeria would have defected to APC if the tide is not controlled.

3. Methodology

Research design

Descriptive survey research was used. It was deemed most appropriate for the study.

Population of Study

Fifty seven respondents formed the sample for the study. We randomly selected this number based on ethnicity, political alignment and selected political analysts. The population had diversity in terms of age, sex, social economic status, and experience among other variables. Census study was adopted because the population was manageable.

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Method of data collection

The mixed method of data collection was used. We used primary tools of data collection and secondary instrument together. Questionnaire items were used to source data from the respondents. The items in the questionnaire addressed the variables of study. The ease of access to the respondents by the researchers, allowed for a personal administration of the instrument which ensured hundred percent return rate thereby eliminating non-return bias. In depth interviews were conducted with the 57 respondents as a follow-up to the questionnaire in order to glean the subtle aspects that questionnaire items could not adequately elicit. In-depth-interview focused mainly on the respondents' justifications for particular response options to questionnaire items. Also, we utilized focus group discussion guide. Data were also collected from records and internet resources.

Method of Data Analysis

Responses that were relevant to the objectives and hypotheses formulated were used. The method applied in the analysis was difference in proportion, and, in testing the hypotheses formulated, Z-test was used.

Table 1: Mass defection to All Progressive Congress (APC) will lead to one party system and bad governance.

	Yes	No	Total
No of respondents	39	18	57
Proportion	0.68(P ₁)	0.32(P ₂)	1.00

4. Presentation and Analysis of Data

The aim of the analysis is to test for significant difference between the proportions of responses P₁ and P₂. Because the sample size was not large and the parameter, assumed to be normally distributed, the test concerning that parameter is carried out using the Z-test. It is used in testing the hypotheses H₀: P₁ = P₂ (i.e. P=0.5) as H₁: P₁ > 0.5). This is obviously a one-tailed test.

$$Z = \frac{P_1 - P_2}{\sqrt{\frac{Pq}{n}}}$$

Where

P₁ = the proportion of the population that say 'yes'

P₂ = the proportions of the population that say 'No'

q = 1 - P

P = 0.5

n = sample size

Test of Hypotheses

(1) Mass defection and its attendant one party system in Nigeria will lead to misrule and governance deficit

(2) Mass defection to the ruling party and its attendant one party system in Nigeria is a prelude to authoritarianism and dictatorship.

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$$\frac{\sqrt{0.68 - 0.32}}{(0.5)(0.5)} = 5.4$$

Using the normal distribution table at $\alpha = 0.05$, the tabulated Z – value is 1.645, hence one-tailed test for equality of the two; proportion (i.e. H_0) is rejected in favor of H_1 . Conclusion therefore, is that P_1 is significantly greater than P_2 .

Decision – Since the value of Z – calculated is greater than the value of Z – tabulated, the H_0 is rejected.

Conclusion: P_1 is significantly greater than P_2 which means that there is relationship between

Table 2:

	Strongly agree	Agree	Disagree	Not sure	Total
No of respondents	28	19	7	2	58
Proportion	0.5	0.33	0.13	0.04	1.00

Since there are four responses, the natural thing is to assume, under H_0 that the proportion of responses are equal, hence assumption is that $P = 0.25$.

$P_1 = 0.5$, $P_2 = 0.33$, $P_3 = 0.13$ and $P_4 = 0.04$ and compare them each with the population proportion of $P = 0.25$.

$$\text{So } \frac{\sqrt{P_1 - P}}{\sqrt{P(1-P)}}$$

mass defection to the ruling party and its attendant bad governance in Nigeria

Hypothesis 2

H_0 : Mass defection to the ruling party and its attendant one party system in Nigeria is not a prelude to authoritarianism and dictatorship.

H1: Mass defection to the ruling party and its attendant one party system in Nigeria is a prelude to authoritarianism, dictatorship and totalitarianism.

For ‘Strongly agree’

H_0 : the proportion of P_1 is 0.25 (i.e. $P_1 = p$)

H_1 : P is not equal to 0.25 (i.e. $P_1 \neq P$)

Test statistics Z, since sample size is large (i.e. $n > 30$)

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N

$$= \frac{0.5 - 0.251}{\sqrt{\frac{(0.25)(0.75)}{56}}} = 4.32$$

For $\alpha = 0.05$, for a two-tailed test, Z from the normal distribution table is 1.96.

Decision: - Since the calculated Z (4.32) is greater than the tabulated Z (1.96), H_0 is rejected.

Conclusion therefore is $P_1 \neq P$ hence, sufficient evidence abound that the proportion of Z

$$= \frac{0.5 - 0.251}{\sqrt{\frac{(0.25)(0.75)}{56}}} = 1.38$$

For $\alpha = 0.05$, the tabulated Z = value is 1.96. Since Z = - calculated is 1.38 which is less than 1.96 H_1 is accepted. Conclusion is that the proportion who agree to the opinion is not significantly higher than 0.25.

For 'disagrees' 'Not sure' opinions, it can be seen that the figures are very small. Considering the result from 0.33 figures an inference can be made that the outcome of the 'disagree' and 'not sure' opinions will not be significantly higher than 0.25. And this will amount to testing the obvious.

Conclusion: Since the general opinion is that mass defection and one party system will lead to authoritarianism, dictatorship and totalitarianism.

respondents who strongly agree is significantly greater than 0.25.

There is also need to test 'Agree' responses for significant difference from $P_1 = 0.05$

The procedure is to carry on as before'

5. Summary of Findings, Conclusion and Recommendations

5.1 Summary of findings

The study revealed among others that:

- 1) Mass political defection to the ruling APC party in Nigeria will lead to misrule, politics of prebendalism and governance deficit. This is because the country would have turned into a single party system without any organised opposition.
- 2) Mass political defection to the ruling party APC will lead to authoritarianism, dictatorship and oligarchic regime in Nigeria if the situation is not arrested now.
- 3) Mass defection to the ruling party will also expose Nigeria's weak political structure

5.2 Conclusion

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Political defection has become a reoccurring trend in Nigeria's political landscape and a ploy to derail the fledgling and weak democracy. The ugly trend undermines ideological divide among parties. It also disrupts legislative and judicial functions. It has significant implications for the growth of Nigeria. If not halted, it could easily lead to anarchy, chaos, ethnic conflict, mass distrust on government and its attendant mass protest.

The issue of political defection, no matter how we ignore it, may obfuscate the prospect of the Nigerian fledgling/authoritarian democracy.

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5.3 Recommendations

- 1) The electorate should ensure that they get their voters card and come out to vote.
- 2) The civil society organisations (CSOs) should speak out on this evil political development in Nigeria which if not checked could lead to the replication of General Sani Abacha's model of democracy and dictatorship.
- 3) All the ethnic groups in Nigeria and the masses should close ranks to fight this hydra-headed monster which is likely result to one party system.

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